

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS RELIANCE JIO: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract - In May 2016, Jio launched a bundle of multimedia apps on Google play as part of its upcoming 4G services. Jio sim is more compatible to most of the apps than other sim cards make in to penetrate in to the market. From the previous literature there are a smaller number of observations extracted by the previous researchers. Thereby the present paper focuses in knowing the satisfaction level of customers on the usage of Jio sim, placing it as its major objective. Further it went on fulfilling two objectives such as analysing the impact of demographics on the overall satisfaction level of users and extracts different reasons associated with them. In order to meet these objectives, the paper has organized a survey method using a schedule on 192 respondents, those are survey using simple random sampling. the results have stated that the respondents are not complete satisfied with usage of Jio sim. The strong reason behind their dissatisfaction is its speed i.e. the users are not getting the same speed all the time. The other two more reasons identified are compatibility of other sim cards, call connects, voice call connects. The reasons where the customers are mostly satisfied are cost effective, free calls, no roaming providing free channels, providing free caller tunes, voice clarity. Even it is found that the demographics hardly affects their satisfaction level Finally it is suggested to improvise the situation of Jio sim by considered the reason stated above where the customers shared their dissatisfaction level. The present paper can further know to usage places its statement is better analysis in future.

Keyword: Simple random sampling, satisfaction level, speed, connect the call first.

INTRODUCTION

Now –a- days, no one is living without mobile phone. So many numbers of network services are available in this world. The present study focuses on reliance Jio network which has been founded in 2007. It is a Long-Term Evolution (LTE) mobile network operator in India. It is the own subsidiary of reliance group headquartered in Mumbai which provides wireless 4G LTE service network and is the only 100% volte operator in the country. It covers all 22

telecom circles in India. The reliance Jio has appointed Sahrukh khan as their brand ambassador. Jio have to issue 15 billion new shares at Rs.10, each to existing shareholders.

Reliance communication owns and operates the world's largest next generation IP enabled connectivity infrastructure which comprises of 4,80,000 kilometres of fibber optic cable system in India .Reliance group ranks among India's top private sector business houses in terms of net worth. The company has a good customer

base and it covers pan India. Reliance jio is in process to set-up the 4G LTE under the banner of Reliance **Jio Infocomm Limited (RJIL)**.

High speed internet connectivity, rich communication services and various digital services are offered by Jio. The key domains such as education, healthcare, security, financial services, government citizen interfaces and entertainment are the mostly benefited by jio.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Customer pleasure is an advertising time period measures how merchandise or services period by way of an employer meet or surpass a customer's expectation. Now days Customers are greater conscious. Customers have eager remark closer to the product brands, due to the fact from this they get outstanding delight extra than benefits. The importance of this learn about is to make research on customer's views, delight and problems concerning JIO SIM.

Reliance Jio has entered into the market of telecom service providers with freebies and more data to the customers. In the knowledge world, Jio's the foray into the fast-evolving market has made tremendous change in the competition, price and data availability. Jio is widely used by the techno-savvy customers. The customer satisfaction is conditioned by the price, availability and addressing the problems of the customers at once. The rural area

customers also use Reliance Jio. Even though the sector has reflected promising growth in India but still remaining at a very low compared with international standards and this providing tremendous opportunity for future growth in Tele-communication services. So, Reliance Jio improves the network connection and speed in rural areas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate the satisfaction level of Jio sim users.
2. To analyse the impact of demographic variables on the overall satisfaction level of Jio sim.
3. To understand the consumer awareness level towards reliance jio sim.
4. To identify the reason to buy the reliance jio sim.

Hypothesis

H₀-There is no significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and customer care problems of respondents.

H₀-There is significant relationship between qualification of the respondents and aware of jio reliance.

Limitation of the study

- The respondents were mostly within the income of middle and lower class.
- The research was carried out in a short period of time.
- Limited sample size 120 respondents.

Review of literature

R. SornaPriya and Sathya, (2017)¹, in their study titled, "customer satisfaction towards reliance Jio network started that fifty two percent of the respondents are cosy with Jio offerings and sixty four percent of them had been counselled to improve its community coverage.

KR. Mahalaxmi and Suresh Kumar N (2017)², in their study titled, "changing the Indian telecom sector: reliance Jio printed that the promotional gives of Jio enables extra clients to decide on Jio and majority (97 percent) of the respondents had been comfortable with the offering of Jio.

B. Boobalan Et al (2017)³, in their study on "customer pleasure towards reliance Jio sim with special reference to Dharmapuri district" made a try to understand the pride level of multi customers. Most of the clients are selecting relianceJio is comes underneath for sim playing cards are free and most of the customers for appreciation the profits and delight stage of Jio services is comes beneath between (10001 – 20000). Finally conclude that most of the clients are comfortable with the current Jio services.

Dr. Gowthamichintala et al (2017)⁴, in this article entitled, "customers delight in the direction of telecommunication service provider-A learn about on Reliance JIO" is to be aware of the pride level of the customers. The gender wise analysis of the client's

pride is concluding that there is no distinction in the opinion of male and female respondents on the pleasure level towards the provider furnished by the JIO services.

Research methodology

Research Methods is defined as "tools or instruments used to accomplish the goals and attributes of study".

Method of data collection

The data was collected for this study is

- **Primary data:** The primary data are those which are collected as fresh for the primary time.
- **Secondary data:** Secondary data is collected from journals, magazines and books, newspaper and internet.

Area of study: This study was conducted in Coimbatore city.

Sample size: The sample size is 120.

Tools used for analysis: Data analysing tools are Simple percentage and Chi-square test.

Simple percentage: Percentage base analysis helps to find which factors is significant among several factors.

Chi-square: A chi-square statistic which is used to test the measures of expectations compare to actual observes (or) model result.

Analysis and Interpretation

Demographic profile of the respondents

S.no	Demographic		No of respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	71	59%
		Female	49	41%

2	Age	Below 20	18	15%
		20-30	40	33%
		30-40	30	25%
		40 above	32	27%
3	Qualification	Below HSC	6	5%
		Under Graduate	66	55%
		Post Graduate	18	15%
		Professional	30	25%
4	Occupation	Student	41	34%
		Professional	22	18%
		Business	22	18%
		Others	36	30%
5	Income	Below 10000	48	40%
		10000 to 20000	34	28%
		20000 to 30000	30	25%
		30000 above	8	7%

Interpretation: Table 1 clearly states the demographic profile of the sample respondents. Majority of the respondents fall in the age group of 20-30 and most of them are Male. Majority of them are under graduate students. Majority of the respondents are students. Most of the respondents' income level is below 10000.

Chi-Square Analysis

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$$

Degree of freedom = (r-1) (c-1)

H₀: There is significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and customer care problems of respondents.

Chi-Square Table

particular	Df	Chi-square value	Table value	Remark
Gender and customer care problem	3	4.2495	7.815	Accepted

ms Jio user				
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Source: primary data

Significant level = 0.05

Result: calculate the chi-square value is (4.2495) is less than (7.815) table value hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is found that there is significant relationship between respondents' gender and customer care problems of respondents.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between qualification of the respondents and aware of jio reliance.

Chi-Square Table

Particular	Df	Chi-square value	Table value	Remark
Qualification and aware of jio reliance.	9	16.919	51.74	Rejected

Source: primary data
Significant level = 0.05

Result: The calculate chi-square value is (16.919) is higher than (51.74) table value hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between qualification and aware of jio reliance.

Finding

1. It is understanding from the survey the 59% respondents are male.
2. It is found that majority of the respondents 33% are in age group of 20 to 30 years of age.
3. It is exhibited that most of the respondents 55% are under graduate.
4. It is found that majority of the respondents 34% are in students.
5. It is exhibited that majority of the respondents 40% are having below 10000 as their monthly income.
6. It is understanding from the survey the 50% respondents are married and 50% respondents are unmarried.
7. it is found that majority of the respondents 80% aware of this product jio.
8. it is found that majority of the respondents 50% are previously used airtel network before using jio network.
9. It is exhibited that most of the respondents 58% are rate this jio network is medium level.
10. 74% are willing to recommend to others about jio.
11. it is found that majority of the respondents 70% are using prepaid plan.
12. It is exhibited that most of the respondents 62% represent the overall performance of jio is average.
13. It is exhibited that most of the respondents 52% are the various plan offered by jio is good.
14. it is found that majority of the respondents 82% are satisfied with the services of jio.
15. it is found that majority of the respondents 76% are satisfied with the present recharging option of jio.
16. it is found that majority of the respondents 52% are rank of the customer services is good.

SUGGESTION

Most of the respondents are suggesting improving the network coverage of Jio services and decrease the very high price value. It assists reliance jio to capture the greatest market share in current trend. And it can be survived in the market with its competitors for long period and create a good image in minds of customers. Now a days the company increase

their recharge plan, so it will affect the all the Jio user so the most of the respondent's suggestion is decrease the recharge plan. improvement in the customer services will enrich CRM practices and retain existing customer and to create new customer.

Through the word of mouth, the customers are aware of jio and strive for accessing its services. That is why, it is recommended to increase the quality of their services. To remove the network problem and calling congestion, the present study suggests installing the towers in the place of unavailability of network and the remote areas.

CONCLUSION

The study is involved in measuring the level of satisfaction and preference of jio customer and the recharger recommends reliance of jio company to improve their network coverage and decrease the recharge price. And it is assured that the company can achieve the 100% satisfaction of their customer. And also, the customer might not be switch over to other networks.it will create goodwill for the company and enrich its worthiness.

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APPENDIX

1.Name

2.Gender Female

Male

3.Age

20 to 30

30 to 40

40 to 50

50 and above

4.Educational qualification

SSLC

HSC

U.G

P.G

5.Occupation

Student

Professional

Business

Home maker

6.Annual income

Below 10000

10000 to 20000 20000 to

30000 Above 40000

7.Marital status

Married

unmarried

8.Are you aware of this product jio?

Yes

No

9.Through which way did you get to know about jio?

Family

Friends

Tv ads

News

10.Which are the previous network you have used?

Airtel

Vodafone

BSNL

Others

11.What are the problem you are facing in jio sim?

Very high price

Network issues

Limited tariff

12.How would you rate the network of jio?

Low

Medium High

13.Would you like recommend others about jio?

Yes

No

14.Which plan under are you currently using?

Prepaid

Post paid

15.Overall performance of jio is

Bad

Average

Good

16.How do you rate various plan offered by jio?

Excellent

Good

Average

Poor

17.Are you satisfied with the services of jio?

Yes

No

18.Are you satisfied with the present recharging option of jio?

Yes

No

How do you rank customer care services?

Excellent

Good

Average

Poor

20. Give your suggestion if

